

Analyzing Electrical Capacitive Methods of Soil Moisture Sensor Using ANOVA Test

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Abstract— Soil moisture is a major factor in plant growth with soil-based media. In the world of agriculture, accurate and effective measurement of soil moisture is necessary so that plant health can be maintained. The sensor method based on electric capacity is considered to have good measurement effectiveness, this is because it can measure soil density without having to release atoms into the soil. This study aims to determine the electrical capacitive method on soil moisture sensors as well as data collection to determine the effectiveness and accuracy on three different media surfaces, namely free air, soil density and water density. From the measurement results it was found that the sensor could distinguish media or surfaces, the results of errors in data collection were at a threshold below 0.05 in the ANOVA test.

Keywords— ANOVA Test, Soil Moisture, Sensor, Electric Capacitive

I. INTRODUCTION

Sensors have become an important part of technological development. As well as the function of the senses in humans. The sensor works by converting impulses into electrical energy that can be translated. [1] Using a variety of existing sensors, we can determine light intensity, temperature, movement, shock, electromagnetic, the distance between objects, touch, and humidity levels in the air and on the ground. Among all these sensors, the soil moisture sensor is widely used in the world of agronomy and hydrology, to detect threats from natural disasters, and also in the field of horticulture. [2] Soil moisture itself means the level of temporary water availability in shallow soil layers on the earth's surface. [3] Because it is temporally and spatially dynamic, it is necessary to measure soil moisture periodically to make it accurate. This measurement can be done in various ways, which have their advantages and disadvantages, so we must choose the most appropriate and effective method depending on our needs. [2]

Currently, soil moisture measurement sensors have many different methods and also produce different measurement standards. Several methods commonly used are Gravimetric Method, Gamma Attenuation, Neutron Methods, Time Domain Reflectometry, Capacitance and Frequency Domain Reflectometry, Tensiometer Method, Resistive Sensor (Gypsum), Hygrometric Techniques, and others. [2] Many journals have discussed the differences between these various soil moisture sensor methods. Most have focused on

the advantages and disadvantages of these methods, and which sensors are more accurate. One of the studies on sensor comparisons was conducted by Chowdhury, et al. He and his team compared two inexpensive sensors, namely resistive and capacitive sensors in two ways, namely calibration of the sensors in gravimetric and volumetric water content, and the other is the analysis of the response of the sensors when different amounts of water are added to the same amount of soil. The results show that resistive sensors have a lower level of sensitivity than capacitive sensors. However, capacitive sensors have weaknesses in terms of performance and calibration which are not as good as resistive sensors. [4]

Figure 1. Soil Capacitive Sensor Sample [5]

However, there are many types of comparing methods, so it takes a lot of experimentation to determine what levels and types of voltage are most needed for this sensor. In addition, capacitive sensors still have a very wide range in their measurements, and it is difficult for these sensors to distinguish extreme conditions. This is because there are differences in the level of calibration. For example, this capacitive humidity sensor is difficult to distinguish when it is immersed in water or wet ground, and also when it is immersed in dry soil, or when it is left in the air. So, it is necessary to examine whether there is a difference in sensor performance when used in air, water, and soil. [4] The statistical method that is commonly used to find out similarities between variations is the ANOVA test.

Therefore, this study focuses on finding out the appropriate voltage settings for capacitive soil moisture sensors for the media based on a parallel circuit. The data processing technique that will be used in this research is Analysis of variance (ANOVA) is a common test to compare the accuracy results of each classifier. [8]

II. RELATED WORKS

Baskar, Vijaya, A.Lakshmi priya, K.Hemapriya, A.Hemanthkumar and V T Kireeti[1] have conducted research related to land monitoring using echo soil sensors (EC-5) to monitor plantation land using the telemetry method or connecting via the internet. In that study, researchers tested the function of the sensors used. The results obtained by the sensor can read soil moisture and send the measurement information via the internet. Brahma, Muktimani and Goswami, Bikramjit [11] conducted research on features on soil moisture sensors with a resistive type. Researchers conducted observations of the sensor measurement results using an electrically resistive method. The results achieved from these observations are looking up dielectric methods, the electrical resistance methods, and the electrical capacitance methods.

III. EXPERIMENT DATASET AND METHODS

A. Dataset

The data used in this study uses a soil moisture sensor for measurement techniques, and sensor measurement data collected through serial communication connected to the local network (LAN). The data collected has a research objective, namely to see the response of plants to soil moisture measurement.

Continuously every 10 seconds to collect the data. In addition to soil moisture data used as the primary data, light intensity and leaf length on the research object are also collected as secondary data. The writer uses these three data groups as variables for the response to plant development.

B. Methods

In this paper, the authors use several methods grouped into two categories. The first category is the hardware configuration, which uses the electrical capacitance method. Electrical capacitance is the working principle of electric charge capacity in a material that experiences atomic friction. The shape of the sensor is a plate arranged in parallel so that the electricity is charged and then passes dielectric material. The procedure of integration between the electrode plate and the dielectric material is contained in the following formula:

$$C = \frac{Q}{V} = \frac{\oint S \in E \cdot ds}{\int E \cdot dl} \quad (1)$$

The formula above produces a ratio of electric charge (Q) to the potential difference (V), and in case the potential difference is a constant value then the simplify of formula becomes:

$$C = \frac{\in EA}{E\delta} = \frac{EA}{\delta} \quad (2)$$

Based on this formula, the design form of the resulting capacitor component design is illustrated in Figure 2 below:

Figure 2. Capacitive Parallel Plate

In the design of the soil moisture sensor based on the methodology of electric capacitive shown in Figure 2 above, the shape of the sensor is three-dimensional (3D). The surface of the dielectric material of one blocked by the electrodes will store a greater electric charge and reduce the resistance generated from the soil surface will be difficult to be measured. The equation of sensing number getting by moving electrode, the electrode surface is stored parallel to the surface axis with a planar arrangement (2D).

The planar shape design is placed electrode side by side and is influenced by the surface area of the dielectric material. The distance between the electrodes used as a reservoir, the current trapped between the two plates. Due to the influence of the surface area of the dielectric material, the calculation is continuous with the following formula:

$$C = \in G \quad (3)$$

The calculating technique using planar capacitance is inseparable from the area to be measured, how large is the surface of the copper wire strands that will function as electrodes. Then it takes the encapsulated geometric property (G), the sensor electrode as a capacitor plate and get an electric charge it needs to be exposed directly to the soil medium. The capacitive soil moisture sensor is connected to a timer circuit, with the formulation:

$$V = \frac{A}{C} \quad (4)$$

The planar plate design based on the above formula is as follows:

Figure 4. Planar Plate Design Concept

Complications on geometric properties (G) configured on a planar outside of technical analysis. The voltage is defined as a function of the input capacitance of a group with a constant property. Capacitance is not summarized one by one because it requires an area of the geometric property, the volumetric water content in the soil measured to determine the capacitance of the sensor in reading the water content in the soil. Then the volumetric water content in the soil is formulated as follows:

$$\theta_v = \frac{ms/\rho_s}{mw/\rho_w} \quad (5)$$

mw is defined as the mass of water and ms is defined as soil, while ρ_w is the mass of water and soil. The volumetric water content is related to the dielectric content of soil and water by dividing the two.

ANOVA is a technique developed by Ronald Fisher to analyze the differences between groups in a sample. Commonly, the ANOVA test is used to compare the variance between groups relative to the variance within groups [5]. Most statistics provide ANOVA tests, making them more accessible to researchers than any other experimental sciences. It is also easy to put in data sets and run simple ANOVA tests [6]. The statistically significant result, when the probability (p-value) was less than the predetermined threshold (level of significance), justified the null hypothesis being rejected [7].

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

In this research and written in this paper, we will look at the results of the settings and methods for the soil moisture sensor and the results of these settings implemented in the watering command. The results of the arrangement based on the electrical capacitive methods obtained data on the classification of sensor reading groups, including:

1. Sensor placed in free air
2. Sensor placed on the density of water
3. Sensor placed on soil density

Calibration was carried out in a container filled with soil with a volume of 200 ml with a geometric property of 22.75 mg/l, and then the sensor applied an analog reference voltage

of 5 volts and a current of 20 mA. The trial results obtained data in table 1 below:

TABLE I
SENSOR CALIBRATION DATA AND

Mass Container [mg]	Mass Soil + Container [mg]	Sensor Read [v]	Soil Volume [ml]
22,75	62,78	4,98	200ml
Sensor placed in free air	71,51	4,90	
3,15	82,41	4,79	
Water Density	96,94	4,77	
997	109,22	2,80	
Dry soil mass (200ml)	132,37	2,79	
26,33	135,9	1,80	
Soil Density	159,02	1,79	
0,13165	186,76	1,50	

The calibration results show multilevel readings of the resulting voltage, from the lowest voltage of 1.5 Volts and the highest generated voltage is 4.98 V. The classification behavior is programmed through the Arduino IDE platform, the programming logic is written in the pseudocode as follows:

1. **Input** AnalogRead(A0) ← (0 < bit_rate < 1028)
2. Declare sensor_pool
3. Set value sensor_pool = Analogread(A0)
4. Set value result = sensor_pool/1028*5
5. **If** result 2.80 < result < 4.77 do
6. Set state = "DRY"
7. **Else if** result 1.80 < result < 2.79 do
8. Set state = "WET"
9. **Else if** result 1.50 < result < 1.79 do
10. Set state = "WATER"
11. **Else if** result 4.78 < result < 5.0 do
12. Set state = "FREE AIR"
13. **Else do**
14. Set state = "ERROR"

In Figure 3 is a photo of the measurement results on a container filled with soil, then testing on water and testing on free air.

Figure 3. Sensing soil density

Figure 4. Sensing soil density and free air

Based on the results of observations on the calibration, it was found that the voltage drop trend on each different sensor surface, In Figure 5 below, it can be seen that the resulting voltage chart experiences a high resistance thereby reducing the level of electric charge capacity on the surface of the sensor.

Figure 5. Calibration Voltage Range

After the sensor has been calibrated, the next step is testing the planting medium containing plants containing *bak coy* (*Brassica Rapa*) at the age of 0 to 38 days. The sensor takes readings based on the three calibration groups according to table 1, namely the sensor is placed on the ground. The sensor reads the values in the range of 2.22 Volts to 4.82 volts depending on the level of soil moisture. Tests for reading sensor data for the second group were carried out on water-based or hydroponic plant media and obtained data in the range of 4.78 volts to 4.79 volts and tested sensors

placed in free air. The comparison of the results of the three surfaces is:

TABLE II

SENSOR IMPLEMENTATION BASED ON SURFACES

Weeks	Sensor Calibration		
	Free Air	Soil Density	Water Density
Week-1	4.98405175	4.54407939	4.78431875
Week-2	4.94596970	4.03157311	4.78708260
Week-3	4.88983938	3.52245600	4.78819423
Week-4	4.83815756	3.03286817	4.78415571
Week-5	4.82444608	2.84191474	4.78597232

Figure 6. Implementation Based on Surfaces

Based on data from table II, data analysis was carried out using the ANOVA test technique based on the features provided by the number processing application, namely Microsoft Excel, and the results were found in tables III and IV. The test found a threshold (alpha) of 0.05. The results of the ANOVA test show that the p-value is <0.05. That means the accuracy between the three surfaces without significant statistical selection (reject the null hypothesis), it also means that the accuracy of measurements in soil-based growing media produces numbers that vary based on the level of soil moisture and free air and water surfaces tend to be stable.

TABLE III

SUMMARY OF ACCURACY RESULT – WITHOUT FEATURE SELECTION

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
Free Air	5	24.4825	4.8965	0.0046881
Soil Density	5	17.9729	3.5946	0.4949348
Water density	5	23.9297	4.7859	0.0000031

TABLE IV

ANOVA TEST ON ACCURACY RESULTS – WITHOUT FEATURE SELECTION

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	5.210928	2	2.605464	15.64449	0.000454	3.885294
Within Groups	1.998504	12	0.166542			
Total	7.209431	14				

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

From the research conducted and supported by the results of analysis, it was found that the soil moisture sensor based on the capacitance method can measure effectively on different surfaces, and the soil moisture sensor with the capacitance method can distinguish soil density, water density, and free air.

Based on the results of data analysis at the time of implementation, it was found that the sensor can work optimally in approximately one month. This research can be continued by testing the resistance of the sensor material because it found a continuous decrease in the quality of readings on soil density media.

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